

ALTERNATIVE SOFTWARE PLATFORMS FOR THE CONCURRENT ENGINEERING LAB AT TU DARMSTADT, A CONCURRENT ENGINEERING FACILITY FOR MULTIDISCIPLINARY APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Within the framework of the cooperation agreement “Memorandum of Collaboration” between the European Space Agency (ESA) and the Technical University of Darmstadt (TUDa) the “ESALab@TU Darmstadt” initiative was established where concurrent engineering has been one of the key topics and led to the build-up of the Concurrent Engineering Lab (CELab) at TU Darmstadt, focusing on conceptual design of complex technical systems.

This paper presents the result of a comparative assessment of alternative software platforms for the specific requirements of the CELab. It describes the findings of the research as well as the analysis and selection of the software platforms. The most optimal solution resulting from the evaluation was implemented in the CELab in order to validate the software platform based on a pilot use case. The results of this validation and optimisation approaches to the software platform are discussed as well.

1. INTRODUCTION

In 2019, the European Space Agency (ESA) and TU Darmstadt signed a cooperation agreement (“Memorandum of Collaboration”) with the aim of expanding and strengthening the cooperation between the two institutions and providing additional impetus along the entire innovation chain from basic research to space missions. [1]

On the one hand, the cooperation aims to introduce innovative engineering approaches in the area of ground segment and operations, the area of responsibility of ESA’s control centre, the European Space Operation Centre (ESOC) in Darmstadt. On the other hand, the motivation is also to increase the portfolio of research and teaching topics at TU Darmstadt in the field of space through synergies and closer links with ESA/ESOC.

The joint project picks up the concept of an “ESALab@TU Darmstadt”, with a first core element being a facility for concurrent engineering (CE) tailored to the particular needs of Ground Segments and Operations design as well as the entire spectrum of teaching and research at TUDa. CE is a state-of-the-art method within the space industry. This well-proven

concept for designing complex space systems and missions in the pre-phase 0/A with a team of engineers and scientists of different disciplines generates an effective and time efficient design management system [2].

Figure 1. Logo of the Concurrent Engineering Lab@TU Darmstadt

This year, construction works finished of a new facility for CE at the campus Lichtwiese of TUDa. Fig. 1 represents its logo. The chosen location for the “Concurrent Engineering Lab@TU Darmstadt” (CELab) is the mechanical engineering building of the university. First of all, the ESA users will have the chance to get out of their every-day working environment and fully concentrate on the CE process. At the same time, this also facilitates the access to the CELab for the students of TUDa. The layout and infrastructure of the CELab is based on the ESTEC Concurrent Design Facility (CDF) design. Fig. 2 shows the lay-out of the CELab from the front and back side.

Figure 2. Front and rear view of the CELab

However, the specific needs of the Darmstadt's use cases called for a special tailoring of the facility's layout. A horseshoe shaped table forms the centre of the CELab providing for up to ten participants/ technical disciplines workstations, each equipped with a desktop PC. At a front desk the team leader moderates and manages the design sessions. The front desk is located on a platform that accommodates the cabling to connect the workstations for the technical disciplines with the displays, servers and audio-visual equipment which allows the team leader to control the systems via a touch panel. As an extension to the core concurrent engineering table, adjustable tables on the right half of the room can be used to create up to eight additional workstations. They can be used e.g. for specialists who can participate in the session using their own laptops. Optionally the lab can be divided into two rooms by a flexible partition glass wall system creating an additional small meeting room for splinter working or discussion groups next to the main room where CE sessions are taking place. Even more working consoles, be it at TU Darmstadt premises or any other site, can be hooked up through a VPN gateway.

Besides the equipment, the facility also has to provide a suitable software infrastructure to enable efficient multi-disciplinary concurrent engineering.

Although numerous facilities for CE exist within the space sector, the method is not yet fully established for ground segment engineering and operations design studies. For the application within this area the software CE client as well as the integrated design model of the CELab have to be customised to the needs and requirements given by the ground segment. While concurrent engineering for the space segment in the majority of the use cases can be focused on a standardised set of expert disciplines (e.g. power, thermal, data handling, communications etc.), the engineering design problem for ground segments is usually much more diverse. It includes engineering aspects and disciplines, involving often non-space aspects such as for example large scale ground data handling, processing and distribution as well. As a consequence, the design process, the models and tools need to follow diversified requirements in a much more agile way.

On the educational side, the CELab also aims for academic training sessions (e.g. courses, student thesis and research projects from institutes of various faculties). Therefore, it is particularly important that the CE software platform is intuitive and flexible to handle, as the group of participants is constantly changing and long periods of familiarisation need to be avoided.

Therefore, a research, validation and implementation of a client software from existing solutions for the special concerns of the CELab has been carried out. At first, the paper describes in detail the requirements and their further classification for the software. Section 3 explains the method of the selection process and its individual phases with the results. The paper concludes with a summary and outlook.

2. REQUIREMENTS FOR THE CE SOFTWARE

The specific design requirements are given by the needs of prospected users and the dedicated focus on ground segment engineering.

The engineering of the ground segment is the designing of a complex socio-technical system with complex processes. To provide a facility in which the agility and efficiency of concurrent engineering can be thoroughly tested in ground segment engineering, it must be possible to easily accommodate new and non-standard system elements. For example, a larger variety of possible disciplines needs to be taken into account. Also, the team composition can vary widely due to different mission needs.

Additionally, the educational perspective requires a high flexibility. The CELab@TU Darmstadt provides a new environment for research and learning. Also, beyond space-related engineering and mechanical engineering, other departments will use the facility for further research.

As mentioned, the purpose of the CELab is to provide an environment for concurrent engineering studies. The first and most essential need is, therefore, that the software is designed to support CE.

Due to timing and resource constraints, the selection of the respective CE software was not allowed to imply significant new developments, meaning that the software must be readily available and mature enough to work reliably.

To enable innovative studies in the CELab, it is also necessary that the software is customizable to the degree that allows the implementation of new software functions by coding efforts. This is ensured by an open-source software or similarly adjustable software concepts.

The software used by ESA, OCDT, runs on a data model described in the ECSS-E-TM-10-25A technical memorandum. This memorandum regulates data exchange between agencies for CE projects and is intended to become a technical standard [3]. To ensure this compatibility, the software selected in this project shall also comply with this memorandum. This will support data exchange and interoperability between ESA projects as well as other CE projects and projects in the CELab.

When engineering ground segment problems, the resulting products can differ from regular hardware-oriented design and may include aspects not directly associated with conventional space engineering. Therefore, it is necessary that the objects of these classes can be added and edited without being restricted to classical space associated terms and aspects.

The ECSS-E-TM-E-10-25A defines several data classes to describe the CE process and the products designed in this process. These classes shall be creatable and customizable. Referring to the ECSS-E-TM-E-10-25A this includes the classes "Role", "Discipline", "System", "Subsystem", "Element", "Instrument", "Equipment",

“Sub-equipment”. Furthermore, it shall be possible to create and customize system parameters and budgets without big efforts.

As it turned out in the testing campaigns, setting up a CE Session can take significant time. Shortening this effort is especially helpful in academic use, since the time available to introduce students to a software and for them to work on a project is typically restricted. It also seems logical that relying on reusable work environments and user interfaces can save efforts that can be used to maximize engineering output.

Another aspect relevant to studies in the academic context can be the transparency of processes for documentation and teaching purposes. To facilitate this, a revision history would be a valuable addition to a CE software.

Studies at the CELab are intended for cooperation with external partners. This could mean that either participants with computers not directly connected with the CELab work on a model in the CELab or that remote users participate in studies of the CELab. As a consequence, it must be possible to add additional participants to a project from within the network of the TU Darmstadt and from external networks. If the remote access works, it is presumed that the access from within the TU is also possible through VPN structures.

Satisfaction of some of the presented stakeholder needs is non-essential while others are mandatory. To account for these differences, the derived provisions are grouped according to relevant standards.

For this project, those provisions also include preferences, which are non-essential yet still beneficial to the suitability of a software. This means that a software must adhere to all requirements to be a viable candidate, while not adhering to a preference will not exclude the software from further testing.

Requirements and preferences are listed and further divided into two categories as presented in Fig. 3. The two categories represent functional and non-functional requirements, referring to the nature of the feature a software must possess to adhere to the provision. If a given feature is needed to carry out a particular task or interaction, the provision is called functional. For the sake of simplicity, all other provisions are called non-functional since the division of provisions is usually done in a more refined way, which however was not necessary for this project [4].

Figure 3. Classification of the requirements [5]

2.1 List of requirements

The previously explained requirements and preferences derived from the needs of users and process constraints are further specified and presented in Tab. 1. This list also shows how the requirements are tested. As explained, non-functional requirements are tested in the preliminary selection. The tests for the other requirements are performed in the pilot use case.

Table 1. List of requirements

Preliminary selection
Requirement
Concurrent engineering
Available
Mature
Customizable
ECSS-E-TM-10-25 data structure
Functional testing (use-case)
Requirement
Creating and editing a new Role
Creating and editing a new Discipline
Creating and editing a new System
Creating and editing a new Element
Creating and editing a new Subsystem
Creating and editing a new Instrument
Creating and editing a new Equipment
Creating and editing a new Parameter
Creating and editing a new Budget
Preference
Creating, editing, and loading a work environment
External access: external network
External access: internal network
Revision History
Standalone application available
External availability
Free-to-use
Runs on private computers
Manual available and comprehensive

3. SELECTION PROCESS

Finding a software able to provide the needed functions in a user-friendly way is especially important for the CELab since students and researchers should be able to focus on finding innovative solutions to engineering problems, rather than learning to work with a novel software solution.

To find the best possible fit for the CELab, a structured, transparent, and reproducible approach was applied. This ensured that the decision process could be customized for other applications or reviewed regarding its validity. Special attention was paid to provide an objective and fair comparison of the possible software solutions. This comparison was facilitated by a multi-step assessment and selection process.

Fig. 4 shows the five phases of the process. The following chapters explain the procedure of the respective phase in

more detail and show its result.

Figure 4. Phases of the selection process [5]

3.2 Requirement analysis and definition

When defining the requirements for software, the focus should be on the needs of all the stakeholders, especially the user. Those needs are then transformed into a measurable system to specify the needed characteristics of a software to allow for a reproducible approach. This implies, stakeholders must be identified, their needs must be understood and transformed into requirements imposed on the system. [6]

In the case of a CE software, it is especially important to analyze the area in which CE will be used, what tasks will be engineered, and which group of people will use it [7]. This process is to ensure that the requirements are correct, complete, accurate, consistent, and testable [8]. The results of this step are essentially what leads to the specific requirement and preference definitions shown in Tab. 1.

3.3 Preliminary selection

To find the right software, possibly viable solutions were analysed. Narrowing down the variety of those solutions is done by assessing their technical data or consulting people associated with the software, such as regular users or representatives of the developing entity. The assessed solutions are presented in the following paragraphs. This assessment focused on non-functional requirements. Only requirements are used to rule out possibilities, since preferences were considered to not be important enough for ruling out a possible candidate. Only non-functional provisions are tested, because those can be assessed on the basis of technical information.

3.3.1 CDP 4

CDP 4 is a concurrent engineering software developed

and commercially distributed by RHEA Group. RHEA is a provider for different sorts of engineering software. It is used in the private sector for CE studies by corporations like Airbus in their Defense and Space segment. The software is an open-source software and can be used and customized using several programming languages by private users without charge in a publicly available “Community Edition”. The program can be accessed by a graphic user interface (GUI) and a Microsoft Excel Add-in. It also features a toolkit supporting software customization. [9]

3.3.2 CIC-CNES IDM

The French Centre National d'Études Spatiales (CNES) has implemented its own software on their concurrent design facility in 2016. This tool, called IDM, is based on OCDT [10]. Unique about this application is the high degree of interoperability with other engineering software [11].

3.3.3 OCDT

The Open Concurrent Design Tool (OCDT) is developed by ESA and used as the CE application in its CE facilities. The data input is done via a Microsoft Excel Add-In.

In the space-related CE field, OCDT is widely known as a CE software. It is also used for training programs such as workshops for students, giving the software the benefit of users potentially being familiar with the software. [12]

3.3.4 Valispace

Valispace is a CE software developed and distributed by the Valispace AG, a company that is specialized on this specific product. Founded in 2016, Valispace AG is a relatively young company.

The company follows an approach to employ an intuitive user interface.

The tool was already in use by a students' group of TU Darmstadt, the TU Darmstadt Space Technology e.V. (TUDSaT). Therefore, some users already know the software. [13]

3.3.5 Virtual Satellite 4

Virtual Satellite 4 is an internal project by Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt (DLR). It is used in their Concurrent Engineering Facility (CEF) in Bremen and steadily developed as an open-source project since 2007.

Virtual Satellite 4 focuses on a flexible engineering process. [14]

3.3.6 Preliminary evaluation

The results of the preliminary evaluation are presented in Tab. 2. It indicates that OCDT and CDP4 are considered as possible solutions. Therefore, the further evaluation will focus on these.

Table 2. Evaluation of preliminary selection [5]

	CDP4	CIC-CNES IDM	OCDT	Valispace	Virtual Satellite
Concurrent engineering	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Available	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓
Mature	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Customizable	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓
ECSS-data structure	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗
Preliminary result	passed	failed	passed	failed	failed

3.4 Building a rating scale

To objectively compare the different software, a rating scale is introduced.

Comprehensibility and objectivity are assured in this rating scale by keeping it as simple as possible. The scale uses only three notches for the comparison. Lower ratings indicate a better result for the solution. A rating of 1 indicates that the solution fully satisfied the respective stakeholder need in an easy or intuitive way. A rating of 2 indicates that the solution provides the function but in a complicated way. A rating of 3 shows that the software was not able to provide the function. This allows for just enough nuance to differentiate between possible but suboptimal and excellent abilities of a software. It also enables a high degree of objectivity since subjective opinions are forced into precise differentiation.

A final rate for the software is determined by the arithmetic average of the rating grades.

3.5 Further evaluation utilizing a generic function testing

Given the results of the preliminary selection, two software candidates, OCDT and CDP4, are tested in order to assess their compliance with both the functional requirements and preferences defined in section 2.1. Utilizing the rating scale described in section 3.4, their respective performance is rated, as seen in Tab. 3.

Table 3. Evaluation of the generic function test

No.	Requirement	CDP4	OCDT
1	Creating and editing a new Role	1	1

2	Creating and editing a new Discipline	1	1
3	Creating and editing a new System	1	1
4	Creating and editing a new Element	1	1
5	Creating and editing a new Subsystem	1	1
6	Creating and editing a new Instrument	1	1
7	Creating and editing a new Equipment	1	1
8	Creating and editing a new Parameter	1	1
9	Creating and editing a new Budget	2	2
	Preference		
10	Creating, editing, and loading a work environment	1	1
11	External access: external network	1	1
12	External access: internal network	1	1
13	Revision History	2	3
14	Stand-alone application available	1	3
15	External availability	1	2
16	Free-to-use	1	2
17	Runs on private computers	1	2
18	Manual available and comprehensive	1	1
	Final Rating	1,11	1,44

As a result, RHEA CDP4 was retained for deployment and testing in the CELab.

3.6 Validation of decision

With the final selection complete, a validation of the result of the selection process is necessary [5].

For this purpose, a pilot use case, i.e. a hypothetical engineering problem for the GS&O aspects of a space mission, is conceived.

The model task is focused on the on-ground processing of an optical emergency signal of coming from a satellite which is triggered in case of a space link failure. An illustration of the problem can be found in Fig. 5.

Figure 5. Illustration of the pilot use case used for validation [5]

During a realistic CE session, the first iteration of a solution for this problem is engineered.

Moderated by a system engineer, domain experts exchange ideas and information, developing and expanding an engineering model in CDP4 in the process.

4. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

Via the presented selection process, CDP4 by RHEA is picked as the most suitable solution. This decision was shown to meet the requirements of the CELab. CDP4 can be used for various engineering disciplines in the academic environment. In the validation process, CDP4 continued to prove its usability as well as adaptability to new and unconventional areas of engineering.

In the CELab, innovative GS&O solutions can be designed, further strengthening the cooperation between ESA and TU Darmstadt. This will provide interesting topics for researchers at the University and innovation to GS&O.

For students, the CELab is an opportunity to learn the practices of modern Concurrent Engineering processes and allow them to experience design from a unique perspective.

These possibilities are already explored in first CE studies conducted by student project groups in the CELab. These sessions show how innovative engineering brings value for students, researchers and organizations like TU Darmstadt and ESA alike.

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